

KU LEUVEN

LSE

THE LONDON SCHOOL
OF ECONOMICS AND
POLITICAL SCIENCE

UNIVERSITY
OF TARTU

REMEDIS TOOLKIT

- Simplified version -

The REMEDIS consortium includes **seven academic partners** and **14 non-academic cooperation partners**.

REMEDIS Toolkit Structure

1. Introduction

2. Laying the
Groundwork

3. Making it Happen

4. Unpacking the
Insights

5. Telling the Story

6. Continuous
Improvement &
Sustainability

7. Intervention
Evaluation
Recommendations

8. Useful
Resources

Introducing REMEDIS

The REMEDIS project is funded by the EU's CHANSE (Collaboration of Humanities & Social Sciences in Europe) programme.

The project has **two main goals**:

1. REMEDIS aims to create and assess ways to build media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) and understand their positive impacts in different areas of life.
2. REMEDIS aims to find and measure key factors for ML&DS at all ages and to assess how effective current ML&DS interventions are at reaching positive outcomes for participants.

Defining ML&DS

Media literacy and digital skills are related concepts, but they focus on different aspects of interacting with technology, media, and information

- **Media literacy:** The ability to critically analyse, evaluate, create, and engage with media content in various forms.
- **Digital skills:** The abilities required to use digital devices, applications, and tools safely and effectively.

REMEDIS Target Groups & Their Caregivers

- Disadvantaged youth (NEETs - Not in Education, Employment, or Training)
- The unemployed
- Refugees
- People with lower socio-economic status (SES)
- Carers of NEET youth
- (Future) teachers

REMEDIS: Aim & Objectives

The **overarching aim** of REMEDIS is to understand what the impacts of ML&DS interventions in the different life domains are in terms of positive outcomes.

To this end, the project has **four objectives**:

1. Improve theoretical understanding of intervention outcomes.
2. Enhance media literacy and digital skills strategies using current and emerging evidence.
3. Adopt advanced methods to develop and validate evaluation tools.
4. Provide evidence-based policy recommendations and a user-friendly evaluation toolkit.

The Importance of ML&DS

1. **Critical thinking & informed decision making**
2. **Effective communication** → digital interaction, content creation
3. **Civic engagement** → political participation, social movements
4. **Economic opportunities** → job market, entrepreneurship
5. **Personal security & online safety** → online safety, privacy management
6. **Adaptation to technological changes** → remaining digitally literate in a changing landscape
7. **Cultural & social awareness** → diverse perspectives, global connectivity

Media Literacy & Digital Skills

Intervention Context

Media Literacy & Digital Skills Interventions

Media Literacy & Digital Skills (ML&DS) interventions are programmes or strategies designed to enhance individuals' abilities to critically analyse media content and effectively use digital technologies.

- **Media literacy interventions** focus on teaching individuals how to understand, analyse, and evaluate media content critically.
- **Digital skills interventions** aim to improve individuals' ability to effectively and safely use digital technologies.

Media Literacy (ML) Interventions

Typically Cover:

1. **Media formats & platforms** → print media, digital media, broadcast media, social media
2. **Critical analysis of (social) media content**
3. **Mis/disinformation & fake news**
4. **Media influence** → perceptions, attitudes, and behaviours
5. **Education & career development**
6. **Well-being** → balanced media consumption, mental health impact, digital detox, recognising harmful content
7. **Informed consumer choices** → recognising persuasive tactics, emotional appeals, product placement, influencer endorsements
8. **Ethical media consumption** → copyright awareness, trustworthiness, reliability

Digital Skills (DS) Interventions

Typically Cover:

1. **Fact-checking** → evaluating information, critical mindset
2. **Media bias analysis** → analysing bias, assessing credibility
3. **Online communication** → effective messaging, practical applications
4. **Digital content creation & ethics** → creating responsibly, gaining hands-on experience
5. **Digital footprint awareness** → managing online presence, identifying risks
6. **Cybersecurity & online safety** → staying safe online, cybersecurity scenarios
7. **Advanced digital skills (for specific needs)** → building expertise, advanced training projects
8. **Problem-solving & troubleshooting** → effective problem solving, troubleshooting

Importance of Evaluating ML&DS Interventions

- Evaluations ensure **effectiveness**
- Evaluations support the **optimisation of resources**
- Evaluations demonstrate **value**
- Evaluations support **funding**
- Evaluations inform **future intervention programmes**
- Evaluations boost **engagement**
- Evaluations **advance field knowledge**

Challenges Associated with ML&DS Intervention Evaluation

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Start Smart:

Nine Key Principles for Media Literacy Intervention Evaluation

1. Holistic approach
2. Contextual relevance
3. Evidence-based practices
4. Long-term impact
5. Stakeholder engagement
6. Adaptability and innovation
7. Ethical considerations
8. Sustainability
9. Transparency and accountability

Initial Steps

- **Define the Evaluation Purpose & Focus**
- **Intervention Outcome Evaluation:** Impact evaluation & Outcome evaluation
- **Identify the Baseline:** Know Where You Stand to Measure What You Build!
- **Building the Basics:** About the *Theory of Change*?
- **Turning Theory into Action:** Building an Evaluation Framework
- **Securing Funding & Building Evaluation Capacity**
- **Backward Planning:** Defining & Understanding Intervention Outcomes
- **Measuring Success:** Uncovering Key Indicators for Outcomes

Illustrative Framework for Aligning Outcomes, Indicators & Measures

Evaluating Intervention Quality: Meeting Standards for Maximum Impact

1. Relevance
2. Impact
3. Accessibility
4. Engagement
5. Effectiveness of pedagogy
6. Assessment and feedback
7. Sustainability
8. Ethical considerations
9. Innovation and adaptability

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Intervention Evaluation with the Target Group in Mind

- Why it matters: Planning evaluations with the audience in mind ensures **engagement, inclusivity, and reliable results**.
- **Key Considerations** for Audience-Centered Evaluations:

Sampling Types

Random
Sampling

Stratified/Quota
Sampling

Cluster
Sampling

Snowball
Sampling

Volunteer/
Convenience
Sampling

Experimental Design

Quasi-Experimental Design

Non-Experimental Design

Evaluation Methods: Measurement

Quantitative

- Pre-Post Surveys
- Standardized Assessments
- Usage Analytics

Qualitative

- Focus Groups
- Interviews
- Content Analysis
- Observation
- Case Studies

Mixed methods

- Triangulation
- Sequential Explanatory Design
- Embedded Design

Challenges of Research Tool Design

- Variety of Definitions
 - Selection of Indicators
 - One-dimensional Measurement
 - Measurement Scales
 - Subjectivity of Measurement
- Non-standardised Tools
 - Indiscriminate Use of Tools
 - Lack of Alignment with Profession
 - Longitudinal Studies

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Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

- Descriptive Statistics
- Inferential Statistics

Qualitative Data Analysis

- Keeping Track of Qualitative Data
- Turning Data into Stories: Using Anecdotes
- Bringing Research to Life through Stories
- Organizing Information to Find Meaning
- Thematic Networks: Connecting Ideas

Mixed-Methods

- Convergent parallel
- Embedded design
- Explanatory sequential design
- Exploratory sequential design

Advanced Mixed-Methods

- Multistage
- Intervention
- Case study
- Participatory

Personal Data

- Direct identifiers
- Strong indirect identifiers
- Indirect identifiers
- **Personal data protection**
 - Minimisation
 - Pseudonymisation
 - Anonymisation

- **Participants' rights**
 - Consent
 - Informing
- **Data Agreements & Sharing**
 - Joint Controller Agreement (JCA)
 - Data Processing Agreement (DPA)
 - Standard contractual clauses (SCC)
- **Data Storage & Security**

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Evaluation Report: Where to Start?

You can start writing the report once:

- the data are collected and analysed.
- you have identified your audience, their interests, and the purpose of the results for them.
- you have a **software/template** for designing your work and visualising your data.
 - Microsoft Office (Word, PowerPoint, Excel etc.)
 - Survey Monkey - dashboard can also be used for reporting.
 - Canva - design software with available report templates.

Evaluation Report: Structure & Contents

- Executive summary
- Introduction
- Evaluation aims and scope
- Findings
- Limitations and challenges
- Recommendations
- Appendix

Tailoring Findings to Stakeholders

- Who is your intended audience and what are their interests?
- What key numbers your audience needs to know?
- Visualise your data
- Check data anonymity and consent of your participants
- Be transparent: minimize bias when reporting your results

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Structure of Your M&E Plan

Designing

Implementing

Reporting

**Practical
Function**

A solid M&E Plan
makes interventions
more effective

Three Key Questions to Design Your M&E Plan

1. What to evaluate? (Actions, Processes, Outcomes)
2. Why set clear objectives and identify problems?
3. Do you know your beneficiaries?

Key Intervention Characteristics for the M&E Design Plan

Evaluation Planning: Steps for Success

1. Identifying which aspects to evaluate
2. Selecting appropriate methods for data collection
3. Defining the sample to ensure the results are representative and reliable
4. Setting up the evaluation timing
5. Choosing the data analysis methods
6. Defining the success indicators

Continuous Monitoring & Improvement

Ongoing monitoring, continuous feedback, and appropriate tools ensure interventions stay aligned with objectives and improve throughout implementation.

We need to remember **4 key components**:

1. Real-time monitoring
2. Evaluation of intermediate results
3. Adjustments during the intervention
4. Continuous feedback

Analysis of Results & Communication Strategies

Before starting, a clear strategy is essential to analyse the results of the intervention, communicate its impact, and share lessons learned with stakeholders.

This includes:

1. Analysis of results
2. Writing down your results (reporting)
3. Sharing results
4. Using results

Ensuring Effectiveness & Flexibility

Ensure interventions achieve their goals efficiently through continuous review and flexible adjustments during implementation.

We need to remember **6 steps**:

1. The importance of continuous review
2. When to conduct reviews?
3. Who should be involved in the review process?
4. Making adjustments based on reviews
5. Documenting adjustments
6. Communication and feedback on reviews

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Estonia: Spotlight on In-Service Teachers

1. Guarantee Organisational Stability
2. Build Collaborative Partnerships
3. Leverage Digital Literacy
4. Embed Evaluation into Intervention Design
5. Extend Intervention Durations

- Adapt Interventions to Participants' Needs
- Improve Transparency via Better Communication
- Incentivise Participation
- Leverage Cost-Free Interventions
- Use Longitudinal Designs in Measuring Impact

Belgium: Spotlight on Parents with Low Digital Literacy

(Migration & Low-Income Backgrounds)

1. Use simple, relatable language and real-life examples
2. Inclusive & Supportive Learning Environment
3. Encouraging Active Digital Mediation
4. Addressing Digital Literacy Gaps
5. Engaging Fathers & Diverse Caregivers
6. Effective Training & Evaluation

Spain: Spotlight on Secondary School Teachers & Students

1. Engage Non-Academic Partners Early
2. Adapt Evaluation to School Constraints
3. Clarify the Purpose of Evaluation
4. Support Sustainability with Incentives
5. Give Teachers Time to Prepare
6. Tailor Content to Student Diversity
7. Use Long-Term Evaluation Strategies

Finland: Spotlight on Vocational Students & Elderly

1. Adapt Interventions and Materials to Participant Needs
2. Embed Evaluation into Intervention Design
3. Participation of Qualified Trainers and Peer Tutors
4. Incentivise Participation
5. Communicate the Purpose of Evaluation Clearly and Encourage Participation
6. Consider Including Different Methods in Your Evaluation
7. Avoid Survey Fatigue

UK: Spotlight on Low-Income & Refugee Groups

1. Know Your Beneficiaries
2. Adapt to Native Languages
3. Clarify Evaluation's Purpose

Poland: Spotlight on Teachers

1. Adapt Materials
2. Diversify Methods
3. Strengthen Analysis
4. Supportive Learning
5. Qualified Trainers
6. Leverage Tools
7. Monitor Progress
8. AI Awareness

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Further Reading & Resources

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